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Deliverable D3.3 – Digital tools in the project website - preliminary prototype

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COOrdinating and Piloting actions towards Era-hubs as inTer- and intra-regional Ecosystems for knowledge production

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Executive summary

This document, entitled “Digital tools in the project website – preliminary prototype”, presents the rationale and methodology at the basis of the development of the Self-Assessment digital tool, which has been conceived as a proactive instrument to engage place-based innovation ecosystems along the journey to become an ERA Hub. The ERA Hub model, further elaborated from the initial concept and developed within the first six months of the COOPERATE project, is at the core and will be further tested among different ecosystem all over Europe.

With the idea of spurring the creation and/or implementation of ecosystem to become fully-fledge ERA Hubs, the project consortium has drafted two valuable instruments, namely the “Toolbox” and the “Playbook”. The former suggests hand-on tools; while the latter provide guidance on how to use them.

In this framework, one should also place the Self-Assessment (SA), which serves a dual proposal: assessing the maturity level; and providing tools that facilitate the process of becoming an ERA Hub. Therefore, the design of the SA as well as the digital tools is highly related to the work done in Work Package 1 and Work Package 2, in terms of “ERA Hub framework”, “Toolbox” and “Playbook”.

The self-assessment represents a bottom-up exercise, which will allow not only the analysis of the maturity level, but also the creation of a network of stakeholders, engaged in the journey to become ERA Hub. The data collection is based on the “Terms and conditions” requirements reported at the beginning of the assessment.

This document, together with a “look and feel” mock-up of the Self-Assessment (Annex I) and an explicatory calculation file (Annex II), will constitute the “Deliverable D3.3 – Digital tools in the project website - preliminary prototype”, further improvement will be carried out during the project implementation, by month 27.

List of abbreviation/Nomenclature

ACRONYM	STANDS FOR
D	Deliverable
DX.X	Deliverable Number
EC	European Commission
ERA	European Research Area
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
WP	Work Package
SA	Self-Assessment
DT	Digital Tool
MA	Maturity Assessment
ERL	Ecosystem Readiness Level

Introduction: Self-assessment digital tool overview

This document is meant to provide useful insights on the *rationale* behind the definition of both the KPI and the methodology to score the questions/answers provided in the self-assessment (SA). Hence, this deliverable will be divided into sections, each of which tackles one specific aspect of the SA, its characteristics and matrix.

From a broader perspective, the project is willing to enhance the interrelation among citizens and innovation stakeholders, while empowering them to tackle challenges posed both at global and at local levels.

Thus, taking inspiration from the [European Digital Innovation Hubs Network](#), the intention is to provide a tool to accelerate the process for place-based innovation ecosystems of becoming an ERA Hubs, based on a maturity assessment.

Specifically, the self-assessment and digital tool are designed to assess the level of maturity of the above-mentioned ecosystem across Europe, while providing practical tools (based on the Toolbox) and guidance (according to the Playbook) to further advance in the process of becoming fully operational ERA Hub. Besides, the DT follows the logic of modularity and scalability, so that to foster the maintenance also during and after the project. The figure below, summarises the ERA Hub model developed at this stage (Month 8), with related tools, serving as the basis of the self-assessment.

Figure1: ERA Hub model developed within M8

Considering these factors, the SA has been developed according to the definition of following parameters:

- Maturity Assessment for the seven lines of actions (as per the D1.1 - Initial ERA Hub Framework and KPIs):
 - Questions to assess each of the lines;

- Values/weight of each question;
- Types of answers
- Definition of benchmarks to trigger actions through tools:
 - Tools are provided in the D2.3 COOPERATE Toolbox- Release I;
 - Guidelines are based on the D2.1 COOPERATE Playbook - Release I

In addition, the DT foresees a first section of questions, meant to collect users’ basic data; and a second section to understand the starting point of the ecosystem. The third section will focus on the analysis of the level of maturity with specific questions posed for each line of action. Therefore, section 3 will be further subdivided into seven sections. The level of maturity reflects the scale proposed in “D1.1 - Initial ERA Hub Framework and KPIs”, according to which there are 5 level of ecosystem readiness (ERL), reflecting the process of interactions and integration of activities from networking to collaboration.

Overall, the maturity level will be calculated both for single lines of actions, and for the ecosystem as a whole. Finally, based on the level reached, coherent tools will be suggested (see “Assessment result page” of the Annex), allowing the absorption of the ERA Model and the improvement in the process to become and ERA Hub.

Rationale and Matrix

This part addresses the methodology behind the definition of the matrix used to assess the level of readiness. Divided into two sub-parts, the first is devoted to the correlation between the seven lines of actions and the ERL; while the second tackles the relation among the results provided by the SA and the correspondence with the Toolbox and Playbook.

Lines of actions: matrix

Considering that the ERL is based on a 1-5 scale, the SA has to follow the same logic so that to be coherent with the ERA Hub Module provided in D1.1. Before proceeding with the weighting of each question, it is worth to recall the ERL concept:

- 1 = Absence
- 2 = Emergency
- 3 = Development
- 4 = Diffusion
- 5 = Saturation

Based on that, 5 must be considered as the highest level of maturity, while 1 the lowest one. Therefore, each line of action is equally evaluated on a 1-5 scale, having the overall ecosystem gaining a total value of 35, resulting from potentially ERL 5 in all of the seven lines of actions.

In other words, the SA is meant to work on two levels, one measuring the ERL on each line, the other measuring the overall ERL; resulting in the scheme below reported.

ERL FOR EACH LINE OF ACTION	ERL FOR THE WHOLE ECOSYSTEM (7 LINES)
● 1 = Absence	● 1-7 = Absence
● 2 = Emergency	● 8-14 = Emergency
● 3 = Development	● 15-21 = Development
● 4 = Diffusion	● 22-28 = Diffusion
● 5 = Saturation	● 29-35 = Saturation

	LINES OF ACTIONS						
	Research	Talent	Knowledge transfer	Funding	Collaboration	Governance	Innovation
Min-Max ERL level per line	1-5	1-5	1-5	1-5	1-5	1-5	1-5
Min-Max ERL level per ecosystem	1-35						

In terms of the matrix at the basis of the assessment, this follows the ERL logic, thus having 5 as common denominator in each calculation. Before illustrating the matrix in depth, it is worth noting that there are somehow two levels of calculation, different from each other:

- One is related to the set of questions;
- One is related to the whole line of action.

This is due to the fact that each set of question is specifically related to a particular tool. Hence, to have the overall ERL one needs to calculate the level of each single line of action, which may correspond to different set of questions, and thus apply to one or more tools.

Based on that the matrix has been developed as follow:

$$Lx = \sum_{i=1}^{N_T} \frac{5}{N_T} (N_{yi} \times \frac{1}{N_{qi}})$$

$\frac{1}{N_{qi}}$ will result on a number between 0 and 1 since it is calculated as a percentage (1 = 100)

MATRIX LEGEND			
Lx = Line of action	N_T = Number of tools in each Lx	N_{yi} = Number of "Yes" for each tool	N_q = Number of questions for each tool

In order to provide a practical example, everything will be calculated in points, and then translated into the ERL levels. Providing a practical example, one may assume there is one line of action ($L1$), with two set of tools (N_T), having three and five questions (N_q) each, the logic will be the following:

- $L1 = 1-5$ ERL
- N_T1 = evaluated 1-5 ERL but it weights 2.5 in total, meaning that 2.5 pt = 5 ERL
 - Q1 = evaluated in Yes/No --> 0.33 pt yes– 0 pt no
 - Q2 = evaluated in Yes/No --> 0.33 pt yes– 0 pt no
 - Q3 = evaluated in Yes/No --> 0.33 pt yes– 0 pt no
- N_T2 = evaluated 1-5 ERL but it weights 2.5 in total, meaning that 2.5 pt = 5 ELR
 - Q1 = evaluated in Yes/No --> 0.20 pt yes– 0 pt no
 - Q2 = evaluated in Yes/No --> 0.20 pt yes– 0 pt no
 - Q3 = evaluated in Yes/No --> 0.20 pt yes– 0 pt no
 - Q4 = evaluated in Yes/No --> 0.20 pt yes– 0 pt no
 - Q5 = evaluated in Yes/No --> 0.20 pt yes– 0 pt no

Assuming that the user answers Yes for two questions in the N_T1 , while no Yes in N_T2 the value of the whole $L1$ will result in:

$$Lx = \sum_{i=1}^{N_T} \frac{5}{N_T} (N_{yi} \times \frac{1}{N_{qi}})$$

$$Lx = \frac{5}{2} \left(2 \times \frac{1}{3} \right) + \frac{5}{2} \left(0 \times \frac{1}{5} \right)$$

$$Lx = \frac{5}{2} (0,66) + \frac{5}{2} (0)$$

$$Lx = 1,67 + 0$$

$$Lx = 1,67$$

In this case, the L1 ERL corresponds to 1,67 placing the overall line under the “emergency” level.

As a matter of clarity, the correlation between the ERL and the points given to each N_T , is reported below:

ERL LEVEL – INNOVATION	POINTS CORRISPONDANCE (5 pt = 5 ERL)
• 1 = Absence	• 0.00 - 1.00 = Absence
• 2 = Emergency	• 1.10 - 2.00 = Emergency
• 3 = Development	• 2.10 - 3.00 = Development
• 4 = Diffusion	• 3.10 - 4.00 = Diffusion
• 5 = Saturation	• 4.10 - 5.00 = Saturation

Based on that, the ERL of the whole ecosystem results from the total of the ERL reached by single Lx . Translated into the matrix, the whole ERL = $L1 + L2 + L3 + L4 + L5 + L6 + L7$. Assuming that the overall level of the whole ecosystem is 15,88 the ecosystem will be considered under the “development” level.

One feasible way to display this result, is through “radar chart” illustrating the results emerging from each single line of actions, thus showing both those more mature and those less mature, as illustrated in the figure 2. Please note that, a dedicate calculation document, available as excel file and here reported as Annex II has been created to provide a concrete example of the matrix applied. Hence, the case here reported refers to the “Knowledge transfer”, and 15,88 is the maturity level of the whole

Figure 2: Radar chart illustrating the results from the SA

ecosystem, resulting from the excel exercise (see Annex II).

Self-assessment correspondence in the Toolbox and Playbook: matrix

As mentioned before, the idea behind the SA is to accelerate the absorption of the ERA Hub model by place-based innovation ecosystems and local stakeholders and innovation actors. According to the latter, the ecosystem readiness has been identified in 5 different levels, while the degree of interaction has been categorised in four steps, as in the graph below.

Ideally, to have a fully ready ecosystem, collaboration should be in place, unfolded into several actions, such as joint activities aimed at joint goals. Having that in mind, one might easily understand that both the Toolbox and Playbook are meant to support actors in their process of becoming fully-fledged ERA Hubs.

From a general standpoint, the Toolbox provides hands-on instruments to enable actors to further evolve their path towards the ERA Hub. Similarly, the Playbook serves a guidance on how to benefit from the tools, and where to place them within the entire process.

In more concrete terms, the matrix allows the understanding of the level of completion of each section related to a specific tool. Hence, the matrix sequence $(N_{yi} \times \frac{1}{N_{qi}})$ targets exactly this aspect.

In other words, it evaluates in percentage how far a specific tool has been considered. Thus, going back to the example in the previous sub-section “Lines of actions: matrix”

$$N_T1 = 0,66 (= 66\%) \quad N_T2 = 0 (=0\%)$$

meaning that N_T1 does need only few further improvements, while N_T2 requires intense further action. Overall, the matrix will allow the DT to display only the tool related to both N_T1 and N_T2 , as resulting from the SA.

Self-Assessment Digital Tool: Section I “Data”

Section I of the DT is devoted to the collect basic general information about the player taking the SA and thus receiving support, through the Toolbox and the Playbook to further absorb the ERA Hub model. This data is needed to understand the type of actor taking the SA, as well as develop a network of stakeholders engaged in their journey to become ERA Hub. The primary aim of the Section I is not to scrutinise the maturity level, which, on the contrary, is the focus of the whole Section III.

In addition, it is worth mentioning that the first prototype, based on the Playbook and Toolbox, the DT has been developed taking “academia” as primary user. Below samples of question posed in Section I.

General Data:

- Date:
- Name of the player taking the SA:
- Contact person:
- Role:
- Email address:
- Telephone:
- Website:
- Country where the ecosystem is located:
- Full address:

Please note that, before accessing the SA, the user will be asked to agree on the “Terms and Conditions”, also in terms of privacy requirements.

Self-Assessment Digital Tool: Section II “State-of-art and starting point”

Before proceeding with the self-assessment on each of the seven lines of actions, section II is meant to understand the “state-of-art” of place-based innovation ecosystem at the time of taking the assessment. Thus, the idea is to collect quantitative data in terms of, for example, the existence of a quadruple helix paradigm at local scale, the number of researchers engaged in local collaborations, the number and multidisciplinary of departments within the Universities, job market data with specific insights on knowledge-based career opportunities, GDPI invested in the region, etc.

In addition, based on the answers received, this section will provide guidelines to further implement the ecosystem based on the Playbook. The latter is indeed proposing guidelines for the specificities based on the level of maturity. The Playbook differs from the Toolbox, which is gathering all possible tools and is therefore more “hands-on” with respect to the Playbook.

Please note that some questions tackle an aspect which is needed in order to have an effective place-based innovation ecosystem in line with the ERA Hub model. Questions number 1 and 2 below reported, for example, are highly relevant for the essence of the ecosystem in itself.

Possible questions posed and/or pieces of information required at this stage are:

1. Is your ecosystem based on a quadruple helix?
2. How would you describe the level of integration of the ecosystem?
 - 2.1. Absence of integration | Networking | Coordinated networking | Cooperation | Collaboration
3. Research
 - 3.1. How many scientific employees are involved (0-50|50-100...)
 - 3.2. Diversity of research areas: number of different departments/areas/faculties
 - 3.3. Research and development investment: money invested per year in research?

4. Talents
 - 4.1. Employment figures: is there a dynamic job market with high demand for skilled and knowledge intensive professionals (share the ratio of job opportunities)?
 - 4.2. Is there a body overseeing the correspondence in terms of research at academic level, and investment at industrial level to assure coherency to reach common goals?
 - 4.3. Liveability and attractive workplaces for international talent: affordable housing, quality healthcare, good infrastructure, cultural diversity, recreational amenities

5. Knowledge Transfer
 - 5.1. Low barriers to entry: Is there a plan or strategy in terms of inclusive and accessible knowledge transfer processes, simplify bureaucratic procedures, provide financial support, offering mentorship/training?
 - 5.2. Are dedicated personnel available to manage relationships with key stakeholders?
 - 5.3. Engaging formats: interactive/innovative approaches to reach other audiences (workshops, hackathons, informal knowledge sharing events)

6. Funding
 - 6.1. Diversity and availability of funding: government grants, private investments, philanthropic contributions, public-private partnerships
 - 6.2. Transparency: well-defined guidelines, criteria, evaluation processes so funding decisions are fair and objective
 - 6.3. Legitimacy: initial funding validates quality/potential of research project & instils confidence in future funders

7. Collaboration
 - 7.1. Collaboration agreements: formal contract, smaller events, memorandums of understanding, provide framework for collab, ensure clarity and alignment of goals
 - 7.2. Strategic partnerships: sign of solid and stable collaboration, leverage strengths, expertise, and resources of each partner
 - 7.3. Tangible outcomes: joint publications, intellectual property development, commercialization of innovations, policy recommendations, societal benefits
 - 7.4. Trust and openness: open and honest communication fostering supportive/collaborative environment

8. Governance
 - 8.1. Trust and transparency: information readily available, decisions made on sound evidence, clear accountability, openness in communication
 - 8.2. Political support: provide necessary resources, policies, regulations, political leaders recognize value of R&I and advocate for their importance
 - 8.3. Public discourse and open discussion: engaging with citizens, civil society organizations and other stakeholders to gather diverse perspectives, foster inclusivity, ensure well-informed decisions, reflect societal needs and values
 - 8.4. Clear definition of roles and responsibilities: avoid duplication of efforts, ensure effective coordination among stakeholders, efficient resource allocation
 - 8.5. Frequent review of strategy and impact with control mechanisms: regular evaluations, assessments, and monitoring mechanisms

9. Innovation
 - 9.1. Patents: protection of intellectual property and willingness to share discoveries, novel ideas are being generated and protected driving technological progress
 - 9.2. Licensing agreements: allow technology transfer from research institutions to industry enabling commercialization of intellectual property
 - 9.3. Number of start-ups: forefront of innovation, address market gaps and disrupt traditional industries

These questions are indeed a sample of all possible questions to be posed within the framework of the SA and will be further defined within the next activities.

Self-Assessment Digital Tool: Section III “Tools”

As already anticipated, section III investigates the maturity level of both the whole ecosystem and in each of the seven lined of actions, be they:

1. Research,
2. Talent,
3. Knowledge transfer,
4. Funding,
5. Collaboration,
6. Governance, and
7. Innovation

Thus, by posing specific questions on each line and related to single tools, the idea is to measure the maturity level in that area, while starting to gather information to provide a general ERL for the whole ecosystem. Hence, this SA represents a valuable bottom-up exercise to understand and focus on those lines that need to be further improved, while providing samples of valuable tools to engage.

The table below provides an overview of the seven lines of actions and related tools.

	LINES OF ACTIONS						
	Research	Talent	Knowledge transfer	Funding	Collaboration	Governance	Innovation
Tools within the lines	Centres of Excellences	Diversity Outreach	Mentorship Programme	Grants and soft funding	Minisprint	Stakeholder engagement in collaboration platform	Start-up programmes
		Thematic challenges	Populare Science Event		Industry involvement in courses		Strat-up bootcamps
		Contamination Lab					

Section III – Research

This section collects the questions posed by the SA in order to investigate the ERL as far as “Research” concerns. Each question has been weighted 0.25 points. The tool weights 5 pt.

Possible questions posed at this stage are:

1. Establishing centres of excellence
 - i. Were specific areas of research identified?

- ii. Does the ecosystem already have research facilities, state-of-the-art equipment and supportive administrative structures in place?
- iii. Is there sufficient funding to establish these infrastructures and attract new talents?
- iv. Is the necessary talent already in the ecosystem?

These questions are indeed a sample of all possible questions to be posed within the framework of the SA tool and will be further defined within the next activities.

The table below provides an overview of the correspondence among the ERL level and the result reached through the SA

ERL LEVEL – INNOVATION	POINTS CORRISPONDANCE (5 pt = 5 ERL)
• 1 = Absence	• 0.00 - 1.00 = Absence
• 2 = Emergency	• 1.10 - 2.00 = Emergency
• 3 = Development	• 2.10 - 3.00 = Development
• 4 = Diffusion	• 3.10 - 4.00 = Diffusion
• 5 = Saturation	• 4.10 - 5.00 = Saturation

Section III – Talent

This section collects the questions posed by the SA to investigate the ERL as far as “Talent” concerns. Each question has been weighted 0.25 points. Each tool weights 1,66 pt.

Possible questions posed at this stage are:

1. Diversity outreach
 - i. In the ecosystem are there any organizations/entities knowledgeable about diversity challenges?
 - ii. Are there actors specialized in overcoming diversity challenges in these entities?
 - iii. Do these entities have enough funding to work on diversity programs?
 - iv. Are there communities, schools, etc. working towards equality (by implementing diversity programs) around the ecosystem? (Does the ecosystem already have partnerships with these communities, schools, etc.)
2. Thematic challenges
 - i. Is there an entity with specific expertise and credible authority on the chosen theme in the ecosystem?
 - ii. Are the themes chosen relevant and connected to the studies of the interested students? (Does it have a clear connection to real-world problems?)
 - iii. Are there already in place partnerships between the specific industry and educational institution in the ecosystem?
 - iv. Is there enough funding to sustain the costs necessary to develop the challenge and potential awards/recognition?
3. Contamination Labs
 - i. Is there an industrial organisation intended to investigate on a specific topic?

- ii. Is there a group of students dedicated to investigate the challenge posed by the industrial organisation?
- iii. Is there a project manager appointed by the university to supervise the students group?
- iv. Is there a defined sponsorship plan to support this action?

These questions are indeed a sample of all possible questions to be posed within the framework of the SA tool and will be further defined within the next activities.

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• 5 = Saturation	• 4.10 - 5.00 = Saturation

Section III – Knowledge Transfer

This section collects the questions posed by the SA to investigate the ERL as far as “Knowledge transfer” concerns. Each question in the first sequence, corresponding to the tool “Mentorship programs”, has been weighted 0.33 points. Each question in the second sequence, corresponding to the tool “Popular science events”, has been weighted 0.20 points. Each tool weights 2.5 pt.

Possible questions posed at this stage are:

1. Mentorship programs
 - i. Are there experts/professionals available to participate in a mentorship program?
 - ii. Are there fundings to start-off and sustain the expenses of these programs?
 - iii. In the ecosystem, are there parties interested in being mentored? (Are the interest parties big enough to justify starting mentorship programs)
2. Popular science events
 - i. Are there skilled and charismatic science communicators in the ecosystem that are willing to host and present in front of a non-specialized crowd?
 - ii. Does the ecosystem have the infrastructure needed to host such events? (e.g., big enough venue)
 - iii. Are there themes researched by the ecosystem that touch the nearby public and could therefore foster its engagement?
 - iv. Is there extra available funding or eventual sponsorship to cover the costs associated with organizing the event (promotional materials, refreshments, and speaker honorariums, etc.)?
 - v. Does the ecosystem have in place communication lines such as social networks, platforms, websites, local media outlets, community newsletters and partnerships with local organizations/institutions, in order to reach the desired audience?

These questions are indeed a sample of all possible questions to be posed within the framework of the SA tool and will be further defined within the next activities.

The table below provides an overview of the correspondence among the ERL level and the result reached through the SA

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• 4 = Diffusion	• 3.10 - 4.00 = Diffusion
• 5 = Saturation	• 4.10 - 5.00 = Saturation

Section III – Funding

This section collects the questions posed by the SA to investigate the ERL as far as “Funding” concerns. Each question has been weighted 0.20 points. The tool weights 5 pt.

Possible questions posed at this stage are:

1. Grants & soft funding
 - i. Are the themes researched by the ecosystem in line with existing grant and funding initiatives?
 - ii. Does the ecosystem include potential funding partners such as government agencies, philanthropic organizations or industry sponsors willing to invest in research and innovation?
 - iii. Is there a strong network of peer reviewers and experts able to evaluate grant proposals and provide feedback?
 - iv. Does the ecosystem have the infrastructure needed to monitor and evaluate the impact of funded projects?
 - v. Does the ecosystem already have successfully funded projects that can boost its reputation with new investors?

These questions are indeed a sample of all possible questions to be posed within the framework of the SA tool and will be further defined within the next activities.

The table below provides an overview of the correspondence among the ERL level and the result reached through the SA

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• 4 = Diffusion	• 3.10 - 4.00 = Diffusion
• 5 = Saturation	• 4.10 - 5.00 = Saturation

Section III – Collaboration

This section collects the questions posed by the SA to investigate the ERL as far as “Collaboration” concerns. Each question in the first sequence, corresponding to the tool “MiniSprint”, has been weighted 0.33 points. Each question in the second sequence, corresponding to the tool “Industry involvement in courses”, has been weighted 0.33 points. Each tool weights 2.5 pt.

Possible questions posed at this stage are:

1. MiniSprint
 - i. Does the ecosystem have partners that can provide relevant case studies?
 - ii. Are there actors skilled in facilitating and moderating such events?
 - iii. Are there experts on the topic of the chosen case study that can provide guidance and feedback to participants?
2. Industry involvement in courses
 - i. Are there existing partnerships/collaborations between academia and local industries?
 - ii. Did the local industries and academia previously work together on projects/collaborations?
 - iii. Does the academic offering of the university align with the prevalent industry of the region?

These questions are indeed a sample of all possible questions to be posed within the framework of the SA tool and will be further defined within the next activities.

The table below provides an overview of the correspondence among the ERL level and the result reached through the SA

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• 5 = Saturation	• 4.10 - 5.00 = Saturation

Section III – Governance

This section collects the questions posed by the SA to investigate the ERL as far as “Governance” concerns. Each question has been weighted 0.16 points. The tool weights 5 pt.

Possible questions posed at this stage are:

1. Stakeholder engagement and collaboration platforms
 - i. Are the roles, responsibilities, and decision-making processes of the stakeholders and entities of the ecosystem specified in a cohesive framework?
 - ii. Are the objectives, values, and guiding principles of the ecosystem specified?
 - iii. Are there the necessary technological infrastructures to support a collaboration platform where stakeholders can interact (e.g., online portal, dedicated digital platform)?

- iv. Do key stakeholders actively participate in the ecosystem and collaborate with each other?
- v. Are collaboration, inclusivity and open-mindedness promoted by the ecosystem?
- vi. Are there expert moderators/facilitators that can manage the platform, facilitate discussions and ensure constructive engagement?

These questions are indeed a sample of all possible questions to be posed within the framework of the SA tool and will be further defined within the next activities.

The table below provides an overview of the correspondence among the ERL level and the result reached through the SA

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• 5 = Saturation	• 4.10 - 5.00 = Saturation

Section III – Innovation

This section collects the questions posed by the SA to investigate the ERL as far as “Innovation” concerns. Each question in the first sequence, corresponding to the tool “Start-up programs”, has been weighted 0.25 points. Each question in the second sequence, corresponding to the tool “Start-up bootcamp”, has been weighted 0.20 points. Each tool weights 2.5 pt.

Possible questions posed at this stage are:

1. Start-up programs
 - i. Does the ecosystem have the necessary infrastructure/practical accommodation such as access to co-working spaces, labs, prototyping facilities?
 - ii. Are there promising start-ups in the ecosystem that need guidance and financial support?
 - iii. Are there funding initiatives that promote start-ups and their growth?
 - iv. Are there experts with relevant industry knowledge that can provide guidance and mentor entrepreneurs?
2. Start-up bootcamp
 - i. Are there existing relationships between local universities, research institutions, and industry stakeholders?
 - ii. Are there enough interested and upcoming start-ups to justify the program?
 - iii. Is there available funding or are there sponsorships to support the program?
 - iv. Are there experienced mentors and advisors that can guide start-ups? (For example, with previous entrepreneurial experience)
 - v. Are there successful start-ups in the ecosystem that can provide mentorships and guidance?

These questions are indeed a sample of all possible questions to be posed within the framework of the SA tool and will be further defined within the next activities.

The table below provides an overview of the correspondence among the ERL level and the result reached through the SA

ERL LEVEL – INNOVATION	POINTS CORRISPONDANCE (5 pt = 5 ERL)
• 1 = Absence	• 0.00 - 1.00 = Absence
• 2 = Emergency	• 1.10 - 2.00 = Emergency
• 3 = Development	• 2.10 - 3.00 = Development
• 4 = Diffusion	• 3.10 - 4.00 = Diffusion
• 5 = Saturation	• 4.10 - 5.00 = Saturation

Conclusion

Based on the efforts and outcomes performed in the other tasks and the deliverables produced, especially “D1.1 Initial ERA Hub Framework and KPIs”; “D2.1 OOPERATE Playbook - Release I” and “D2.3 - COOPERATE Toolbox - Release I”, the digital tool and the self-assessment have been further developed.

The matrix which has been defined and illustrated in detail within the document provides the level of readiness of the place-based innovation ecosystem, as well as the progression from a state of (1) absence to (5) saturation in each line of action within the ERA Hub Model. Besides, by addressing different cluster of questions and identifying associated gaps towards the ideal ERA Hub according to the model, the matrix is equally able to identify a set of suitable tools to accompany the journey towards becoming an ERA Hub.

The questions presented in the SA points at the different tools available in the “Toolbox”, so that there is a clear interrelation between the level of maturity and the possible tools to be used according to the “Playbook”. The latter acts as guideline to foster the place-based innovation ecosystems’ process of becoming fully functioning ERA Hubs.

Tables of comparison balance the correspondence among ERL of the whole ecosystem, with the level in the single lines of action (Lx). At the same time the matrix relates together the three pillars of the entire SA, namely the seven Lx , the level of completion of the single tools ($N_{yi} \times \frac{1}{N_{qi}}$), and the weight of each tool within the corresponding $Lx = \frac{5}{N_T} (N_{yi} \times \frac{1}{N_{qi}})$.

In addition, this document provides sample questions for each Lx which are weighted to have a clearer understanding of the entire function of the SA.

Finally, this deliverable represents a first prototype: improvements, changes and implementation will be carried out in the upcoming months and finalised by month 27, based on the further improvements and actions carried out within the project implementation.

Annex I

This Annex represent the first mock-up of the Self-Assessment, related to the prototype. These slides are willing to provide a more “look and feel” experience of how the SA is designed. Further improvements will be made throughout the project.

DIGITAL TOOL – SELF ASSESSMENT PAGE

Self Assessment Page 1 of 7

Level 1: RESEARCH
This section collects the questions posed by the SA in order to investigate the ERL as far as "Research" concerns. Each question has been weighted 0.25 points. The tool weights 5 pt.

	Yes	No
Were specific areas of research identified?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Does the ecosystem already have research facilities, state-of-the-art equipment and supportive administrative structures in place?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Is there sufficient funding to establish these infrastructures and attract new talents?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Is the necessary talent already in the ecosystem?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

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DIGITAL TOOL – ASSESSMENT RESULTS PAGE

Self Assessment Page 1 of 7

Results

ERL - SEVEN LINES

RESEARCH: 5,00
4,00
3,00
2,00
1,00
0,00

INNOVATION TALENTS KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER FUNDING COLLABORATION GOVERNANCE

Suggested Tools

- Research**
Centres of Excellences
- Collaboration**
Minisprint
Industry involvement in courses
- Talents**
Contamination Labs
- Innovation**

Annex II

This explicatory calculation has been carried out on Excel and represents the actualisation of the matrix through concrete examples, based on the questions above listed for each line of actions.

Maturity level resulting from the seven lines of actions, calculated on the ERL scale

Questions Nt1 - Centres of Excellence		Yes/No	Value
1	Were specific areas of research identified?	NO	0
1	Does the ecosystem already have research facilities, state-of-the-art equipment and supportive administrative structures in place?	NO	0
1	Is there sufficient funding to establish these infrastructures and attract new talents?	NO	0
1	Is the necessary talent already in the ecosystem?	NO	0

YES	0,25
NO	0
(Ny * Wy)	0

Questions Nt2		Yes/No	Value
1		NO	0
2		NO	0
3		NO	0
4		NO	0

YES	0,25
NO	0

LEVEL OF MATURITY SINGLE TOOL 1	0%
LEVEL OF MATURITY SINGLE TOOL 2	0%
RESEARCH - LEVEL OF MATURITY LINE ON A 1-5 SCALE	0,00

Maturity level for the line of action: Research

Questions Nt1 - Talent			Yes/No	Value
			YES	0,25
			NO	0
1	In the ecosystem are there any organizations/entities knowledgeable about diversity challenges?	YES	0,25	(Ny * Wy) 0,75
2	Are there actors specialized in overcoming diversity challenges in these entities?	YES	0,25	
3	Do these entities have enough funding to work on diversity programs?	YES	0,25	
4	Are there communities, schools, etc. working towards equality (by implementing diversity programs) around the ecosystem? (Does the ecosystem already have	NO	0	

Questions Nt2 - Thematic Challenge			Yes/No	Value
			YES	0,25
			NO	0
1	Is there an entity with specific expertise and credible authority on the chosen theme in the ecosystem?	YES	0,25	(Ny * Wy) 0,5
2	Are the themes chosen relevant and connected to the studies of the interested students? (Does it have a clear connection to real-world problems?)	NO	0	
3	Are there already in place partnerships between the specific industry and educational institution in the ecosystem?	YES	0,25	
4	Is there enough funding to sustain the costs necessary to develop the challenge and potential awards/recognition?	NO	0	

Maturity level for the line of action: Talent (tools one and two)

Questions Nt3 - Contamination Labs			Yes/No	Value
			YES	0,25
			NO	0
1	Is there an industrial organisation intended to investigate on a specific topic?	YES	0,25	(Ny * Wy) 0,5
2	Is there a group of students dedicated to investigate the challenge posed by the industrial organisation?	NO	0	
3	Is there a project manager appointed by the university to supervise the students group?	YES	0,25	
4	Is there a defined sponsorship plan to support this action?	NO	0	

LEVEL OF MATURITY SINGLE TOOL 1	75%
LEVEL OF MATURITY SINGLE TOOL 2	50%
LEVEL OF MATURITY SINGLE TOOL 3	25%
TALENTS - LEVEL OF MATURITY LINE ON A 1-5 SCALE	1,25

Maturity level for the line of action: Talent (tool three)

1	Questions Nt1 - Knowledge Transfer	Yes/No	Value
1	Are there experts/professionals available to participate in a mentorship program?	YES	0,33
2	Are there fundings to start-off and sustain the expenses of these programs?	NO	0
3	In the ecosystem, are there parties interested in being mentored? (Are the interest parties big enough to justify starting mentorship programs)	YES	0,33

YES	0,33
NO	0

(Ny * Wy) 0,67

1	Questions Nt2 - Popular Science Events	Yes/No	Value
1	Are there skilled and charismatic science communicators in the ecosystem that are willing to host and present in front of a non-specialized crowd?	NO	0
2	Does the ecosystem have the infrastructure needed to host such events? (e.g., big enough venue)	NO	0
3	Are there themes researched by the ecosystem that touch the nearby public and could therefore foster its engagement?	NO	0
4	Is there extra available funding or eventual sponsorship to cover the costs associated with organizing the event (promotional materials, refreshments, and speaker)?	NO	0
5	Does the ecosystem have in place communication lines such as social networks, platforms, websites, local media outlets, community newsletters and partnerships with	NO	0

YES	0,2
NO	0

(Ny * Wy) 0

LEVEL OF MATURITY SINGLE TOOL 1	66%
LEVEL OF MATURITY SINGLE TOOL 2	0%
KNOWLEDGE - LEVEL OF MATURITY LINE ON A 1-5 SCALE	1,67

Maturity level for the line of action: Knowledge Transfer

1	Questions Nt1 - Funding	Yes/No	Value
1	Are the themes researched by the ecosystem in line with existing grant and funding initiatives?	YES	0,2
2	Does the ecosystem include potential funding partners such as government agencies, philanthropic organizations or industry sponsors willing to invest in research and	YES	0,2
3	Is there a strong network of peer reviewers and experts able to evaluate grant proposals and provide feedback?	YES	0,2
4	Does the ecosystem have the infrastructure needed to monitor and evaluate the impact of funded projects?	YES	0,2
5	Does the ecosystem already have successfully funded projects that can boost its reputation with new investors?	YES	0,2

YES	0,2
NO	0

(Ny * Wy) 1

1	Questions Nt2	Yes/No	Value
1		NO	0
2		NO	0
3		NO	0
4		NO	0

YES	0,25
NO	0

LEVEL OF MATURITY SINGLE TOOL 1	100%
LEVEL OF MATURITY SINGLE TOOL 2	0%
FUNDING - LEVEL OF MATURITY LINE ON A 1-5 SCALE	5,00

Maturity level for the line of action: Funding

1	Questions Nt1 - Collaboration	Yes/No	Value
1	Does the ecosystem have partners that can provide relevant case studies?	YES	0,33
2	Are there actors skilled in facilitating and moderating such events?	YES	0,33
3	Are there experts on the topic of the chosen case study that can provide guidance and feedback to participants?	NO	0

YES	0,333333
NO	0

(Ny * Wy) 0,666667

1	Questions Nt2 - MiniSprint	Yes/No	Value
1	Are there existing partnerships/collaborations between academia and local industries?	YES	0,033
2	Did the local industries and academia previously work together on projects/collaborations?	YES	0,033
3	Does the academic offering of the university align with the prevalent industry of the region?	YES	0,033

YES	0,333333
NO	0

(Ny * Wy) 1

LEVEL OF MATURITY SINGLE TOOL 1	66%
LEVEL OF MATURITY SINGLE TOOL 2	10%
COLLABORATION - LEVEL OF MATURITY LINE ON A 1-5 SCALE	4,17

Maturity level for the line of action: Collaboration

1	Questions Nt1 - Governance	Yes/No	Value
1	Are the roles, responsibilities, and decision-making processes of the stakeholders and entities of the ecosystem specified in a cohesive framework?	YES	0,166
2	Are the objectives, values, and guiding principles of the ecosystem specified?	YES	0,166
3	Are there the necessary technological infrastructures to support a collaboration platform where stakeholders can interact (e.g., online portal, dedicated digital platform)?	NO	0
4	Do key stakeholders actively participate in the ecosystem and collaborate with each other?	NO	0
5	Are collaboration, inclusivity and open-mindedness promoted by the ecosystem?	NO	0
6	Are there expert moderators/facilitators that can manage the platform, facilitate discussions and ensure constructive engagement?	NO	0

YES	0,166667
NO	0

(Ny * Wy) 0,333333

1	Questions Nt2	Yes/No	Value
1		NO	0
2		NO	0
3		NO	0
4		NO	0
5		NO	0

YES	0,2
NO	0

(Ny * Wy) 0

LEVEL OF MATURITY SINGLE TOOL 1	33%
LEVEL OF MATURITY SINGLE TOOL 2	0%
GOVERNANCE - LEVEL OF MATURITY LINE ON A 1-5 SCALE	1,67

Maturity level for the line of action: Governance

1	Questions Nt1 - Innovation	Yes/No	Value	YES	0,25
				NO	0
1	Does the ecosystem have the necessary infrastructure/practical accommodation such as access to co-working spaces, labs, prototyping facilities?	YES	0,25	(Ny * Wy)	0,25
2	Are there promising start-ups in the ecosystem that need guidance and financial support?	NO	0		
3	Are there funding initiatives that promote start-ups and their growth?	NO	0		
4	Are there experts with relevant industry knowledge that can provide guidance and mentor entrepreneurs?	NO	0		
1	Questions Nt2 - Startup Bootcamp	Yes/No	Value	YES	0,2
				NO	0
1	Are there existing relationships between local universities, research institutions, and industry stakeholders?	YES	0,2	(Ny * Wy)	0,6
2	Are there enough interested and upcoming start-ups to justify the program?	YES	0,2		
3	Is there available funding or are there sponsorships to support the program?	YES	0,2		
4	Are there experienced mentors and advisors that can guide start-ups? (For example, with previous entrepreneurial experience)	NO	0		
5	Are there successful start-ups in the ecosystem that can provide mentorships and guidance?	NO	0		
LEVEL OF MATURITY SINGLE TOOL 1		25%			
LEVEL OF MATURITY SINGLE TOOL 2		60%			
INNOVATION - LEVEL OF MATURITY LINE ON A 1-5 SCALE		2,13			

Maturity level for the line of action: Innovation